

IMPROVEMENT THE TECHNOLOGY OF TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES - AS A SOCIAL NECESSITY AND A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14273184>

Abstract. *The given article presents the stages of training future teachers for professional activity based on the level of reconnection of target, content, organizational and activity, analytical and result components of the structure.*

Keywords: *civilization, habituation, expression of needs, openness to communication, independence, adaptive, reflexive, axiological.*

It is important to suggest that the prospects of civilization of any society depend on its educational status, the structure and essence of the new educational system, its deep educational culture. After all, a high level of education is the only factor that ensures the future of society, state and nation, determining its influence in the world.

Definitely, for achieving these goals, first of all, it is necessary to comprehensively teach the young generation the basics of scientific knowledge, to form in them a broad worldview and a wide range of thinking, to effectively organize educational and upbringing work on the formation of a spiritual and moral worldview. After all, the creation of a bright future for the country, the wide dissemination of its name, the demonstration to society of the national and cultural heritage created by our great ancestors, ensuring that our independent republic takes its place among the developed countries, serve for upbringing of the young generation as a wonderful person and a qualified specialist.

It has been determined that attention should be paid to the preparation of future specialists for professional activity in order to ensure that the bearers of professions operating in various spheres of public life know their professional laws and act in accordance with them.

The scientific novelty of the study is as follows:

-the stages of preparation of future teachers for professional activity (adaptive, reflexive and axiological) have been determined based on the level of repeated involvement of the purposeful, substantive, organizational and activity-based, analytical and result-based components of the structure of continuous professional practice;

-the social and pedagogical content of preparation of future teachers for professional activity has been improved based on an empirical assessment of the results of activities aimed at developing moral competencies (habituation, expression of needs, openness to communication, independence);

-pedagogical opportunities to ensure the integrity and continuity of the process of preparation for professional activity have been improved based on the expansion of modular educational opportunities in organizing and conducting educational processes, summer teaching practice, educational and technological and qualified teaching practice;

Besides that, the technology of training future teachers for professional activity has been improved based on the development of individual problem, case-task complexes, ensuring the speed of formation of constructive structural foundations for preparing students for project activities.

Practical results of the study:

Methodological recommendations for improving the modular technology of organizing qualified pedagogical practice of students have been developed;

Criteria and indicators of preparing students for professional activity by means of qualified pedagogical practice have been clarified;

The electronic system for organizing and conducting qualified pedagogical practice of students has been improved;

A model for preparing students for professional activity has been developed and implemented in educational practice.

The reliability of the research results is based on the methods and techniques used in the work, the theoretical information used within its framework and obtained from official sources, the analysis presented on the basis of empirical research, and the effectiveness of the experimental work based on mathematical statistical methods, conclusions and recommendations applied in practice, the results explained by the fact that they are approved by the competent authorities. It can be also determined by the fact that it is based on scientific and methodological developments created in our republic and abroad, and the experience of practicing teachers.

Scientific and practical significance of the research results.

The scientific significance of the research is that it is enriched with theoretical approaches related to improving the technology of training future teachers for professional activities; with the development of criteria and indicators for determining the level of training for professional activities of future teachers, as well as scientific and methodological recommendations that provide a positive solution to the research problem, personal and professional components, as well as with the revision of standards. The attitude of students to the profession is explained.

The practical significance of the research lies in the scientific and pedagogical description of the activities of future teachers in the process of professional pedagogical practice, identifying its unique pedagogical features, clarifying the qualification requirements for general professional and special subjects taught to prepare students for the profession, the development of scientific programs at the output determined by the clarification of competencies for preparing future teachers for professional activities.

The purpose of the qualification practice:

- consists in the perfect preparation of students for future professional activity, consolidation, improvement and deepening of theoretical knowledge obtained by students as a result of studying the courses, consolidation of methodological knowledge from a practical point of view, provision of pedagogical education and upbringing, further development of practical skills and qualifications, expansion of the worldview;

- expands and consolidates the acquired knowledge of students and teaches them to apply it in practice;

- develops students' interest and love for their profession;

- encourages independent and creative work, regular study of advanced pedagogical practices, creativity in professional activity;

- prepares for teaching preschool children;
- possesses professional competencies for preparing preschoolers for school education at the required level;
- expands and deepens the knowledge in preschool pedagogy, child psychology and methodological sciences;
- controls regular monitoring of classes of advanced teachers and analyzes the observed classes, identifies achievements and shortcomings and provides methodological consultations;
- develops professional qualifications and skills inherent to the group of educators, development of pedagogical skills;
- during the internship, studies the best practices of teachers and training them to conduct training independently;
- carries out educational and coaching work in assigned groups;
- observes training, participation in cultural and educational events and formation of the organization.

Objectives of the qualification practice:

- equipping students in the system of higher educational institutions with individual aspects of the educational process, educational and spiritual activities;
- formation of professional qualities of a future teacher capable of meeting the requirements of the development of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan in the process of building a strong democratic legal state with a changing market economy and an open foreign policy;
- fostering respect and love for the teaching profession and pedagogy in students;
- formation of professional qualifications and skills in mastering the methods of teaching and education in students;
- formation of students' skills in the practical application of theoretical knowledge obtained in the course of teaching social, special and psychological-pedagogical and methodological sciences;
- approaching the pedagogical activity of students from the point of view of creative research, developing skills of regular analysis of the results of their work, studying their pedagogical experience, constantly enriching their knowledge.

What is more important, pedagogical practice carried out in pre-school educational organizations - the ability to independently organize the educational process and other activities, work with children and parents, carry out research work related to the qualifying graduation work, theoretical and practical knowledge is formed. Teaching is strengthened, issues of deepening pedagogical knowledge and further improvement of pedagogical skills are resolved; they will acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in organizing and managing pre-school education - they will be able to positively apply the main tasks facing pre-school education in institutions.

During the teaching practice, each student develops their own attitude to the chosen profession, interest in teaching activities, and level of training in this area. Based on the results of the theoretical analysis, the following five-stage structure of effective preparation of future teachers for professional activities was determined (see Table- 1)

It should be suggested that the theoretical analysis was conducted on the basis of the theoretical idea, scientific data, and practical results recorded in printed and electronic sources as a result of scientific research conducted on the research problem or related topics. The analysis revealed the direction, volume, and scope of research aimed at developing a positive attitude

towards the practice of preparing foreign countries and future teachers for professional activity, the most important idea put forward in them, and the essence of scientific activity. According to practical and methodological recommendations, the study was considered appropriate.

Figure 1.1. The main stages of organizing pedagogical practice in preparing future teachers for professional activity.

Moreover, the following tasks were solved during the study: collection of material based on professional activity performed on topics close to the research problem or related to it; direction based on a substantive study of the collected literature, determination of the theoretical idea, scientific data, and practical methodological recommendations set out in them; critical study of the theoretical idea, scientific data, and practical methodological recommendations determined on the basis of existing research, as well as an assessment of their practical implementation; further enrichment of the assessed theoretical idea, scientific data and practical methodological recommendations; substantiation of the methodology, allowing them to be directly applied in practice through the formation of independent ideas of the dissertation candidate regarding a positive solution to the selected problem; practical testing of the methodology, aimed at developing the skills of preparing future teachers for professional activity. This is a place for training in qualified pedagogical practice, advanced work experience, a school of excellence.

Undeniably, the given the specifics of the preschool education sphere, it is important to explain to future teachers the social nature of their profession.

It should be noted that K. Abdukarimov assessed the situation as follows: “At present time everyone is an educator, the right mother is the first educator, the family is an educator, neighbors, micro district, kindergarten, school, high school are public educators. Education is professional and relevant in a legal civil society that is moving towards great goals.” [8]

It is important to suggest that the goal of pedagogical practice in preschool educational organizations is to familiarize students with the life of a preschool educational organization, its educational and pedagogical processes. Studying the current tasks of preschool educational organizations and following them.

The main objectives of the practice:

- study, observe and analyze the processes associated with the development and upbringing of preschool children;
- familiarizing the employees of the preschool education department, republican preschool educational organizations related to the preschool education system with the training center and the toy exhibition;
- learning to conduct educational work based on theoretical knowledge obtained from preschool pedagogy, child anatomy and physiology;
- preparing students to conduct various pedagogical processes using methods that promote the activation of children's cognitive activity;
- teaching students to control the work of a preschool teacher, to work as a teacher, to conduct educational work in a group of children and individually.

Definitely, analyzing pedagogical, psychological and methodological literature, it was found that the teaching aid created to prepare future educators for professional activity, "initially provides a model of pedagogical practice, in which the stages of pedagogical practice are based and pedagogical practice is carried out. The criteria for establishing are given" [6].

Accordingly, the criteria for organizing pedagogical practice are the following:

- the educational nature of pedagogical practice;
- a character developing pedagogical practice;
- strengthening and development of pedagogical practice.

It is known to everyone that this manual defines the didactic and methodological foundations of the practice process, goals and objectives, which are aimed at preparing future educators and teachers for professional activity. Also, the ideas, rules and requirements given in the manual are adapted for all faculties of pedagogical universities. This manual occupies a unique place in covering the research problem. However, there are specific aspects of the educational process in preschool educational institutions, and it is important to pay attention to the shortcomings that need to be eliminated in this regard:

1. Failure to create teaching aids covering pedagogical practice in preschool educational organizations.
2. Lack of cooperation between parents of children and the teaching staff and lack of attention to social support.
3. Lack of improvement in the process of preparing students for school.
4. Teachers have not improved the psychological and pedagogical approach to solving existing controversial issues.
5. The presence of shortcomings in preparing students for independent learning, observation and a creative approach to professional activity during practice.

For the solution of the problem of modernization of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, major reforms are being carried out. The main goal of the preschool education organization "Concept" created in this area is to improve the process of preschool education in all aspects and increase its effectiveness. Preschool educational organization "Concept" consists of five departments, in which special attention is paid to educational goals, objectives, principles, forms, means and methods. The preschool education organization "Concept" pays special attention to the work of the educator and the owner of the teaching profession in implementing the tasks set for preschool education. The social significance and effectiveness of the work of a teacher of a

preschool educational organization depends on the level of his professional training. This process is based on the principle of a differentiated approach to professional training. State requirements for the development of preschool children are developed in accordance with the Law "On Preschool Education and Training", the Standard of Preschool Education. The tasks set for the development of preschool children are clearly defined in the state standard of preschool education, which defines the standards for the development of a child of each age and indicators that make it possible to assess the achievements and level of development of the child. This document, first of all, provides for the comprehensive development of the child in the family, helping to effectively prepare him for schooling through the correct organization of training.

The purpose of the "State Requirements for Preschool Education" defines the content of preschool education and ensures equal rights for all children and each child regardless of the form of ownership of preschool education organizations, aimed at preserving the dignity of childhood.

Besides that, the fact that the conditions created in preschool educational organizations are not at the required level caused some difficulties in organizing educational and upbringing activities based on pedagogical technologies.

Qualified pedagogical practice was organized on the basis of two stages:

- 1) effective organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations;
- 2) study the management of preschool educational organizations.

In this process, future educators gained knowledge about the work plan and activities of the educator, methodologist, director of the preschool education organization, studied the rating sheets of children's development, acquired the skills of analyzing the indicators of the criteria specified in them.

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